

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF INDIA'S NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020 AND THE EUROPEAN UNION'S EDUCATION POLICY

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ABSTRACT:

This paper analyzes the 2020 India's New Education Policy and the European Union's Education Policy. It can be said that India's New Education Policy, as well as the European Union's Education policy was facing a new challenge in the Covid-19 pandemic Era. In India, education is one of the fundamental rights of individuals, and it plays a pivotal role in the all-round development of the country. In this direction, the study of India's New Education policy plays an important role in understanding the policy aspects in a better way. In the same way, the Education is one of the fundamental rights of individuals of most European Union member countries. Therefore, all the EU member countries perceive a need to increase the quality of their education and develop access to learning at all stages of life. From this, lifelong learning has become the basic point in the EU's educational strategy. This concept includes all the stages and forms of education and combines them. This study focuses on the educational policy of the European Union, which aims to maintain collaboration and integration among its members within the framework of shared cultural values.

KEY WORDS: National Education Policy 2020, European Union's policy, Knowledge-driven, Values, Social integration, Technological development

INTRODUCTION:

Education plays an important role in the growth and development of society. Educated people are more than an asset to the development of society. This made successive governments under different Prime Ministers give utmost importance to investing more money and resources in the field of Education. Education gives people knowledge, skills, and techniques to understand their rights and duties. It also gives a new direction to the country and to the world. Education also gives knowledge about injustice, violence, and corruption in society. Education differentiates human beings from animals. In this context, the study of India's New Education Policy 2020 and the European Union's Education policy gives detailed information to understand India's new education policy in a better way.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

In the light of the above, the proposed research aims to understand the following:

- To understand India's New Education Policy 2020 and the European Union's Education policy.
- To analyse India's New Education Policy 2020 and the European Union's Education policy.
- Internal debate on India's New Education Policy 2020 and the European Union's Education policy.
- Impact of Covid-19, India's New Education Policy 2020 and the European Union's Education policy.

METHODOLOGY:

This work on “A Comparative Study of India’s New Education Policy 2020 and European Union’s Education Policy” is basically an analytical work. The proposed study will largely rely on primary sources, including official Government documents and publications. The study also proposes to hold interviews with the concerned policymakers and discussions with the experts. The study will also critically examine the secondary sources available on the subject matter, such as books, journals, periodicals, magazines, and tertiary sources such as newspapers.

ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS:

INDIA’S NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020:

After India’s independence, many programmes were introduced to increase the literacy rates in rural and urban areas. In this regard, the successive Prime Ministers introduced various policies to enhance primary and higher education in India. In this scenario, for the first time, Mrs Indira Gandhi's government introduced the national policy on Education in 1968. Again in 1986, during Rajiv Gandhi’s period introduced national Education policy. This was later modified during the P.V. Narasimha Rao period in 1992. Then, the national curriculum framework for designing NCERT textbooks was introduced in 2005.

With the aim to bring revolution in India’s education system, the Narendra Modi government appointed a committee under the chairmanship of former ISRO Chief K. Kasturirangan to prepare a draft on the National Education policy. The Committee submitted its first draft in 2018 to the Union government. The government then opened this draft for public suggestions and comments for two years. Finally, the Union government, headed by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, approved the New Education Policy on July 29, 2020. Overall, it can be said that the New Education Policy 2020 had the goal of remodelling the education system to meet the requirements of 21st century India.

FEATURES OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020:

- 1. Increased Budget Allocation-** According to the Union budget of 2020-21, India had allocated 4.6 % of its total GDP on education. It can be said that this greatly benefited in implementing the New Education policy provisions.
- 2. Increased GER and Equitable and Inclusive Education-** According to the New Education policy, the government plans to achieve a gross enrolment ratio of 50% by 2035 and promote multi-disciplinary and inclusive education. It aims to reduce the ratio of dropouts among students.
- 3. Curriculum and Pedagogy in schools-** The New Education policy had introduced 12 years of schooling with three years of Anganwadi or pre-schooling and replaced the 10 + 2 structure of school curricula with a 5 + 3 + 3 + 4 curricular structures.
- 4. Undergraduate Education for 3 to 4 years-** Under the New Education policy, the undergraduate education was extended from 3 to 4 years.
- 5. Teachers Recruitment and Deployment-** Under this New Education policy, teachers are recruited through a transparent process.
- 6. Promotion of Indian languages-** The New Education Policy has emphasised mother tongue or local language or regional language as the medium of instruction at least till Grade 8.

7. **Transforming the Regular System of Higher Education-** According to the New Education policy, the four institutional structures carrying out the functions of regulation, accreditation, and funding and academic standard settings will be set up as four independent verticals within one umbrella institution, the Higher Educational Commission of India.
8. **Technology Use and Integration-** Under this New Education policy, it is said that a dedicated unit for the purpose of orchestrating the building of digital infrastructure, digital content and capacity building will be created in the MHRD to look after the e-education needs of both school and higher education.
9. **Internationalisation of education-** Under this New Education policy, India will be promoted as a global study destination providing premium education at affordable costs, thereby helping to restore its role as a Vishwa Guru.
10. **Graded Autonomy among Institutions-** Under this New Education policy, the University definition will allow for a wide range of institutions, ranging from research institutes to research teaching universities and the Autonomous degree offered by the Colleges.

EUROPEAN UNION'S EDUCATION POLICY:

The European Union was formed by the six European countries, namely Germany, France, Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, and Luxembourg, after the Second World War. This means, basically, this Union was established to set up an economic union between these six European countries. In the early period of its formation, the scope of the organisation was restricted only to the Coal and Steel Sector, which was then extended to include the atomic energy research and development through Eurotom and economic activities through the European Economic Community, which was established in 1957. Later, the assistance was stretched to many economic areas and gradually to foreign and security matters, impacting to Countries politics, economy, foreign policy and society.

In the later stages, the European Union's educational policies emerged with the aim of carrying out internal market obligations, depending on economic justifications. Slowly, the European Union started to give importance to educational policies to provide a cultural and social integration for achieving the aim of political and economic integration. It was said that the European Union's education policy emerged from the social, political, and economic factors. And the European Union considered Education as an important instrument to fulfil the demands of equality and justice in society.

The EU sees its education policy as a national activity, and it also has the objective to facilitate the community's other activities. It also believes that education consolidates harmony among the citizens by supporting foreign education and exchange of students and teachers, and empowering the European Union's integration. Ultimately, it was said that it contributes to applying different policies on community, environment, unemployment, research and technological development, etc.

CONCLUSION:

Overall, it can be said that the New Education Policy is a great vision to change the educational system in this country. This means the purpose of education is not only to add grades, years, and certification but also to build a healthy society. In this direction, the National Education Policy 2020 makes this vision very clear in its agenda. It can also be said that this New Education Policy gave a clear message to the country in need of an education

policy that is in accordance with Indian values, and at the same time, this policy provides global standards to the country's education system. In this regard, the famous educational expert, Sen Gupta, says that "this is a National Education Policy that offers Choice, Chance and Change." But, the biggest challenge to the National Education Policy today in the era of Covid-19 epidemic was the implementation of the policy initiatives into practice. In this direction, the access, equity, quality, affordability, and accountability are considered as the main pillars of the National Education Policy. On the other hand, the European Union's Education policy has the goal to make social and economic challenges coming with globalisation. In this direction, it can be said that the European Union has aimed since its inception to cooperate with the member countries in the field of education and to develop a constructive policy in this area. When compared to India's New Education Policy 2020, in the European Education policy, it can be said that there are some deficiencies in practice despite the number of people benefiting from the programme. However, by solving these, the desired goals can be reached.

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